

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES OF EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Is considered by many countries as a tool that allows to achieve highly efficient k k e due to division of labor, specialization, innovative production and rational use of technological capacities and optimization of use of all kinds of resources.

of production organization has spread rapidly, especially in the last 20 years, and in developed industrial countries, especially Japan, the United States , the European Union, and developing countries. It is becoming one of the important factors of the high rate of economic development in India, China, Vietnam, and Turkey . According to experts' calculations, the share of industrial cooperation in the production industry of developed countries is in the range of 25-35%, and in the production of electronic equipment, road construction equipment, aircraft and a number of other products, it is 50-70%. According to Nikkei estimates, about 10,000 to 9,800 of the parts that make up a modern car are produced through industrial cooperation, including cross-country cooperation.

The following are the main advantages that the economy can get from the development of industrial cooperation:

1. It leads to a significant reduction in the preparation time for the production of new products and a decrease in their capital capacity. According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, interstate industrial cooperation agreements reduce the preparation time for new production by an average of 14-20 months compared to the establishment only within the framework of one's own enterprise, and also reduce the costs of new production development by 50-70%.

2. Improving the quality of manufactured industrial products. Industrial cooperation makes it possible to achieve more than 90% of the quality level of foreign partner's products, while the internalization of foreign technologies can provide only 70-80% of this indicator.

As Bloomberg pointed out, in the context of a shortage of funds in developing countries, their participation in industrial cooperation is one of the most effective measures for technical re-equipment of industry, expansion of the export direction

of production, achievement of international standards for product quality, and increase in employment.

They are very interested in the experience of China, one of the leading countries in the development of industrial cooperation. A distinctive feature of Beijing's industrial policy is its dual nature, with the country simultaneously attracting foreign industrial companies to the country and transferring production capacity abroad.

Today, China is the world's largest producer of more than 220 categories of industrial products, including steel, cement, and automobiles, and accounts for 38% of the world's machine tools, 41% of ships, and 60% of power generation equipment. By the end of 2022, more than 60,000 foreign-invested enterprises have been established in China, more than 30 percent of which are in the industrial sector. At the same time, the number of Chinese companies abroad has exceeded 20,000. Strengthening industrial cooperation is an important part of building a new type of international relations that includes mutually beneficial cooperation. China is showing its willingness to work with other countries to transfer technology, create more jobs, and thus change the world's unbalanced development and unfair distribution of resources.

China applies the following basic principles in the development of industrial cooperation with foreign countries.

First, to express a balanced approach to the interests and principles of their partners. Chinese companies must strictly abide by the law and fulfill their social obligations when conducting business, including when investing abroad.

Second, to conduct win-win cooperation that effectively promotes industrial cooperation based on equality and mutual benefit.

Third, openness and inclusiveness (full participation in the process), according to which China plans to act strictly in accordance with market principles, adhere to accepted international practices, support companies in making independent decisions, and take full responsibility for their own profits and losses.

It should be noted that the level of cooperation with the international industry in Uzbekistan is still unsatisfactory.

The main limiting factors are:

- a) incomplete and insufficiently active processes of privatization and restructuring of industrial enterprises;
- b) underdevelopment of the outsourcing market in the industry;
- v) frequent changes of the normative legal framework and its insufficient compliance with international standards;

d) the high difference in the level of import duties on components and finished products makes the production facilities, which are largely cooperative, insufficiently active;

e) lack of specialized institutions that provide information to find partners;

f) Low effectiveness of SEZ activity organization.

In order to develop international industrial cooperation, it is possible to propose the following measures:

1. Improvement of the regulatory framework regulating industrial cooperation. A modern legal framework that meets international requirements is an important factor in the development of industrial cooperation and requires attention to its development : first , clear regulation of relations between cooperating parties; secondly, creation of state structures directly involved in the development of industrial cooperation ; thirdly, it envisages various measures to encourage and support industrial cooperation entities.

2. Improving the business environment takes into account many situations. In particular:

a) acceleration of privatization of state assets in order to stimulate the entry of foreign capital and technologies into the industry;

b) optimization of regulation of tax and customs tariffs in the industrial sector;

c) reducing administrative barriers, ensuring the necessary quality and developing law enforcement practice.

Directing national companies to organize industrial production in foreign countries . The outsourcing of some industrial products by Chinese companies allows them to "bring back" technologies, special knowledge, and leading brands and products that help transform the Chinese economy and meet the growing needs of Chinese consumers .

The central task of the policy conducted in the oil and gas industry should be to maintain and develop advanced basic industries, which constitute priority technologies for the industrial complex, and provide all other adjacent industries with modern raw materials.

Table 1

Features of the industrial policy of the most economically developed countries

Countr	Objectives	Tools, institutions
Japan	Within the	The combination of self-production policy (structural and

	<p>mework of the heral policy of onomic liberalization luction of the ditional role of owledge-intensive ustries based on port-oriented velopment</p>	<p>novation) selected with "indirect" methods (budget, tax, money, export) will be of increasing importance in the future . The main regulator of industrial policy is the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry. The main instrument of the ministry is structural policy (selective industry programs and regulation of industrial structure). Structure vity politics It applies legislative bodies in the field of antimonopoly legislation . Development and implementation of macroeconomic policies of industrial policy (monetary, tax, budget) is the collective competence of the Bank of Japan, the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry. Foreign economic policy is also a collective "product" of a number of departments . The Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Ministry of Finance rely large state credit institutions (Export -Import Bank, development Bank) in their activities .</p>
<p>Norway</p>	<p>paid to increasing competitiveness of industry in general , d developing the port of the oil and gas lustry . To support e more harmonious velopment of the lustry in the regional vironment and rease efficiency</p>	<p>Among the main methods of industrial policy, the improved system of public procurement and orders, accelerated appreciation , financing and wide application of research and development. These measures are largely indirect methods (tax v credit concessions, economic programming) influence i filled ough. The network regulation system and mechanism relies the active participation of the state in a number of key sectors (transportation, electric power, communication), as well as on the active specialization of the industry for export based on the oil and gas complex . Indirect impact measures on the private sector industry through budget, tax, financial and credit, including protectionist customs policy.</p>

<p>Italy</p>	<p>Development of scientific and technical base, strengthening of competitive positions in the industry, small and medium - sized enterprises in the domestic and foreign markets and activation of the development of agriculture . The main focus is on the development of the energy sector</p>	<p>Reform of institutional structures (privatization) and development of legal framework. Development of state programs support small businesses through preferential tax, credit, appreciation mechanisms, innovation policies . Development of a state program to encourage energy conservation, finance the research for energy resources, and build power plants. Considering the complexity and multiplicity of state bodies involved in the regulation of industrial development and the development of measures. The complexity of the state's influence on the industry, on the one hand, allows influencing and stimulating industrial development in many areas, and on the other hand, creates the problem of insufficient coordination of inter-agency barriers and mechanisms of industrial policy.</p>
<p>South Korea</p>	<p>Security accelerated industrial growth, increasing the role of the industry due to the integration of the achievements of scientific development to the world, openness, improvement of the institutional and organizational structure, foreign capital, technology, know-how</p>	<p>By liberalizing the conditions for the entry of foreign companies into the industrial market, South Korea has begun to structure large companies in the direction of attracting foreign capital to them . They improved the financial and credit system connection with the interests of industrial development. Support for the development of small and medium-sized businesses by subsidizing the training of highly qualified specialists has been dramatically increased through selected tax, credit, foreign economic policy instruments, and the development of industrial policy is under the authority of the Ministry of Trade and Industry . Among the instruments of industrial policy, the types related to foreign economic relations have a special place (investment and tax policy to attract foreign capital, promotion of growth and protection of export-oriented industrial industry from foreign competition, patent policy for the purchase of foreign goods and scientific and technical innovations). .</p>

World experience shows that there are many examples of at least three types of policies in the oil and gas industry: export-oriented (creating conditions for the growth of exports in order to expand certain types of products); internally oriented (protection of the internal market and economic self-sufficiency); aimed at limiting the use of its natural and non-renewable resources (oil, wood, environmental conditions).

Table 1.3 shows the general features of the policy of economically developed countries in the oil and gas industry .

in terms of regulation of the oil and gas market seems interesting. Characteristic features of the American energy market include :

- strict restriction of the use of foreign capital in the production of hydrocarbons ;
- system is used for the right to conduct research ;
- efficient the law safe gi ;
- a strict anti-monopoly policy that ensures equal market access for companies , excluding the monopoly position of any of them even in the territory of a separate state;
- regulation on the oil and gas complex [1].

There are thousands of private mining companies operating in the US market . At the same time, no tax is charged for the extraction of minerals . Greater profitability is required. Oil production is debureaucratized. in Uzbekistan management is carried out through a budgetary planning system with minimal opportunities for rapid correction .

Domestic oil producers in the US have the ability to respond quickly and flexibly to market changes . The presence of a large number of small oil refineries completely eliminates the problem of selling the produced oil . Thus, there are more than 8,000 small and medium-sized enterprises in the United States.

Canada the following is effective is implementing the paths :

- ensuring effective use of the soil ;
- prevent unwarranted depletion of reserves;
- ensuring export efficiency from a national point of view ;
- the use of land based on the principles of interest.

flexible land use taxation system: tax rates are regulated, "tax holidays" are provided and a system of discounts is applied. Royalties depend on oil price, well flow rate, oil quality, field type, production and transportation costs , directed to discoveries.

Such incentive mechanism the search for new fields and fields creates the basis for a systematic increase in the efficiency of oil production. Income tax - 40.8-45.8%, including federal - 28%, regional budget allocations - 12.6-17.8%. According to experts' calculations , the share of the state in oil production revenues is 45-52%. Also, one of the main areas of regulation is the promotion of domestic and foreign investment .

Foreign Investment Act, Canada's interests in resource efficiency ,

environmental protection, commercial interests, support for geological exploration (including direct subsidies), export controls (including repatriation controls) There are conditions for their engagement that provide .

Export revenues, protectionism against resource-rich but underdeveloped regions imposes an obligation to take into account the interests of the local population . Also such measures, prohibits the use of offshore schemes, prohibits the participation of the heads of state- owned companies in the creation of their own firms , including those that can be used to withdraw offshore assets , and controls the company's income [2] .

major oil-producing countries, revenues from oil exports are absorbed by the national economy. The situation is different in the Arab monarchies , where large oil revenues are absorbed by a small population [3].

The first place in terms of oil and gas reserves is occupied by the Near and Middle East. In recent decades, the countries of this region have been among the top ten oil and gas producing countries in the world . The oil and gas industry is completely nationalized and oil companies are controlled by the state.

Major oil-exporting countries in the Middle East have been very successful in investing in Western economies through targeted investments in the structures of multinational corporations and major international financial institutions (including the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the International Monetary Fund).

Saudi Arabia's foreign investments already amount to hundreds of billions of dollars , most of which are directed to the United States. Kuwait dozens of British, Canadian, American, Western Europe and Japan aimed at companies. In addition three oil refinery of Kuwait three of which have factories in Europe , including Denmark, the Netherlands and Italy. Kuwait Denmark, It has thousands of gas stations and ten aviation gas stations in Sweden, Great Britain, Italy and Norway . Stations at major airports in Western Europe . Kuwait, which has a fleet of 25 tankers , actually has a significant portion of the oil it produces today in its own marketing network (the entire cycle from production to sale). Profits from foreign capital investments are becoming an increasingly important source of national income [3] .

Thus, one of the strategic directions of the oil field and the policy of the Middle Eastern countries is to create an infrastructure for oil refining and sale of oil products abroad , which is the acquisition of assets of foreign oil companies that allow effective control of the full cycle of production, processing and sale.

Norwegian experience is also of practical interest , in which oil and gas industry It has a large share in GDP . Industry is the country's largest source of

income, as well as the most important factor of technological and innovative development .

2022 , the oil and gas sector accounted for 23% of GDP, 30% of state budget revenues, 52% of export earnings , and 29% of total investment. Norway is the seventh largest oil exporter and the third largest gas exporter in the world .

From income oil and gas industrial orientation foreign is a fund for accumulation and stabilization of securities , which ensures the long-term stability of the country's budget system . The Norwegian government forms the policy of the oil and gas sector, implements long-term planning in the industry .

L areas where licenses may be issued , conducts geological prospecting in unexplored areas , stock assessment . The state supervises the implementation of projects at all stages , requiring enterprises to prepare a drilling program, discovery report, production plan, transportation plan, mining plan , and compliance with them . The Ministry of Energy and Petroleum is responsible for formulating Norway's energy policy . It also plays a key role in issuing licenses . Operational control over compliance with the terms of the licenses is carried out by the Norwegian Petroleum Administration , which is subordinate to the ministry [4] .

the Norwegian oil and gas complex is the chosen management model , the main element of which is state regulation .

The state initially develops an effective program for the development of the oil and gas complex and sets the following tasks: national control and participation in oil projects, rational management of resources, high -level technological competence and long-term capacity building. Active involvement of foreign industry leaders , quick attraction of financial and intellectual resources to invest in oil production are among the methods of achieving the set goals . By allowing foreign companies access to its reserves , Norway forces them to conduct technological experiments and train local personnel . Also, multinational oil companies will have to contribute to the financing of project engineering programs . which allows solving many research problems in the country[4] . The high level of development of the economy and social sphere indicates the effectiveness of the policy in the field of the use of underground resources, management of the oil and gas sector and its legal regulation .

Table 2

Gas market of foreign countries

Name of the country	Characteristics
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USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strict restriction on the use of foreign capital ; - the existence of a patent system for the right to conduct prospecting and excavation ; - effective legal security and antitrust politics; - to strengthen the influence of centralized regulation on the oil and gas complex ; - no tax is charged for extracting minerals .
Canada	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - different regulation of the field of subsoil use ; - flexible system of taxation for the use of subsoil ; - encourage domestic and foreign investment attraction .
Near and Middle East	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the oil and gas industry as a whole nationalized; - investment in the Western economy through targeted investment in the structures of multinational corporations and large international financial institutions ; - creation of infrastructure for oil processing and sale of oil products abroad .
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - effective management model, its main element is the state regulation; - national control and projects in the oil sector participation ; - resource management ; - high -tech qualifications; - foreign industry leaders and prompt borrowing financial and intellectual resources to invest in oil production

According to the results of the research , it is possible to distinguish the specific characteristics of the development of the oil and gas industry of the countries under consideration (Table 2) .

Thus, for the further improvement of mechanisms of oil and gas market development , the above approaches are of urgent importance . These include state regulation of industry , a firm stance in protecting national interests , use of oil and gas revenues to invest in the national economy , focus on innovative technologies and others. Studying and rational application of foreign experience increases the efficiency of the Uzbekison oil and gas complex .

When studying the foreign experience in the management and development of the oil and gas industry, it is necessary to study the main problems of the industry in the countries where Uzbekistan is a competitor in the world oil and gas market, as well as the development trends of the global oil and gas complex.

The Russian oil and gas industry, as an integral part of the global industry, is working to formulate scientific ideas about the main directions of increasing its efficiency. The management practices of the Russian oil and gas industry are significantly different from those used in foreign countries. For example, in countries with a liberal approach, private companies can develop mines independently, while the direct participation of the state in production is considered absent or insignificant.

Analyzing the experience of Norway and Great Britain, national oil and gas companies have shown how successful the practice of creating large industrial clusters - centers of innovation and entrepreneurship - that act as production locomotives. Today, these countries are leaders in offshore exploration and production.

It is worth noting that both Norway and Great Britain completely got rid of the American currency. Getting out of "technological dependence" created the basis for their creation of national companies that successfully compete with American companies. At the same time, the strategy of creating a cluster should be well thought out, it is necessary to carefully analyze which sectors will have the greatest energy with gas and oil production: for example, exploration and engineering services, equipment manufacturing or petrochemicals.

Norway and Great Britain are examples of the implementation of the strategy of foreign-oriented import substitution products, which is characterized by the development of the production of national products in a very large domestic market, and then their export to the world market.

Such a mechanism not only made it possible to replace similar products in the national market, but also helped to expand the scope of creating opportunities to export surplus products abroad. Its uniqueness has increased the need to take into account advanced global trends, to implement research and innovation in accordance with the requirements of the foreign market in order to maintain competitive advantages[5].

Thus, the world experience includes the following main directions of the policy of import substitution of equipment and technologies for the oil and gas industry:

- establishment of minimum localization indices for the production of equipment and execution of works, which are mandatory in the implementation of tender purchases;
- establishment of a state body coordinating activities in the field of import substitution policy;
- application of special customs regimes for import and export of equipment or technologies;
- creation of a national company with state participation as an operator of the process of transfer of foreign technologies;
- development and support of the fastest growing market, minimization of obstacles ;
- implementation of the Cluster concept of industrial development.

Also, in Brazil , another major country in the oil and gas industry, the acquisition of property and systems by foreign companies is allowed to be included in localization, even if they are used abroad . This creates a unique system of bonuses that can be taken into account every time the company fails to meet the localization goals set for the execution of exploration or production contracts in Brazil .

Thus, the goal of the " Pedefor Program " in Brazil is to facilitate the situation of operators working with suppliers and contractors of high-tech equipment and to create new jobs . Another innovation of the program is that oil companies can provide localization of the equipment originally leased in Brazil and A QSh [6] .

Brazil is one of the leaders in the world in the development of deep mines. The country has succeeded in creating a local supply chain in the oil and gas industry and optimizing the use of local infrastructure. Domestic companies were forced to improve their efficiency by competing with foreign firms. The interaction of Brazilian companies with oil and gas corporations is increasing.

At the same time, the share of local suppliers in the country's oil and gas industry has exceeded 70 percent, which is mainly dependent on the Petrobras National Company, which is actively promoting the development of engineering and oilfield service firms. The positive effect of import substitution is also transferred to related industries: heavy industry, electronics and automotive industry are among them[7].

it is planned to minimize the economic and technological backwardness of the industry, noting the important role of the state in regulation.

The main priority is the direction of "self-reliance", for which the government provides companies with cheap loans, import quotas, currency controls and a fixed exchange rate. At the same time, the economy was nationalized and Brazil's largest state-run oil and gas company, Petrobras, was created. This strategy plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness of national manufacturers in the domestic market, which has expanded the production of the most important products and technologies for the industry[5].

As a result of the analysis of these foreign experiences, it will be appropriate to support local enterprises in our country, involve domestic contractors more widely, and apply priority to national products. As a result of this, the place of our country in the world will be strengthened.

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